

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4101684

Vidyankur XXII/1 Jan-June 2020, ISSN 2249-1503 | 18-30

Collaborational Co-Existing with the AI: Wedding the Bhasmāsura with Humanity for the Good

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Abstract: ‘Virtual reality’ is the watch word for our times with coronavirus sweeping the whole of Earth keeping us socially distanced; not on the social media platforms though. The virtual reality is the new ‘reality.’ Artificial Intelligence (AI) is at the forefront to make our life viable during this pandemic. Work from home, virtual meetings, online classes are all possible through the AI. Our dependence on AI is on the rise exponentially. Will the AI overcome humanity and rule over us? Should we be threatened by Super Intelligence? As the world gets more and more digitalized the challenge is to be human and not become machines ourselves. The essay is an attempt to make a few suggestions as to how we can be human in the age AI by collaborating with the AI. Being human is to be relational, and for our troubled times Being human is to be collaborational with AI. As humanity evolves the AI also needs to evolve into Meta-Super-Intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Co-existence, Collaborational existence, Meta-Super-Intelligence, Machine Agents, Morality, and Bhasmāsura.

Bhasmāsura, the Legend

The Artificial Intelligence (AI) has so revolutionized the world that its impact on humans is immense. The efficiency and accuracy with which the AI functions make it inevitable for human existence. How far have we gone with AI? How far can we go? When these questions baffle me, I have a philosophical recourse to the ancient legend of Bhasmāsura. Bhasmāsura had the boon to destroy anyone whose head he touched, would turn into ashes (*bhasma*); this caused havoc in the world. Mohini (the Avatāra of Viṣṇu), the enchantress, tricked him into seduction. Bhasmāsura, in pursuit of marrying Mohini, lost himself into her. Mohini skillfully made Bhasmāsura keep his hand over his head while dancing, immediately he was turned to ashes. Thus, the boon became bane.

The essay proposes a few suggestions as to how we can be human in the age AI by collaborating with the AI. Being human is to be relational, and for our troubled times Being human is to be collaborative with AI. As the humanity evolves the AI also needs to evolve into Meta-Super-Intelligence.

Co-existence of Bhasmāsura and Mohini?

I'm so tempted to identify Bhasmāsura with Humans and Mohini with AI. Can the Bhasmāsura and the Mohini co-exist without one being threat to another? Being human in the age of AI would be to live harmoniously with AI and complement one another in making this world a better place to live in. This essay is an attempt to explore the ways and means of living with the AI and discovering a new way of being human without losing our humanness. Quite a task though! Be that as it may, let's plunge into the world of AI and learn to live with the Mohini without getting destroyed.

Evolution of Life

Life is a process that can retain its complexity and replicate. What's replicated isn't matter (made of atoms) but information (made of bits) specifying how the atoms are arranged. In other words, life as a self-replicating information-processing system whose information (software) determines both its behaviour and the blueprints for its hardware. The evolution of life can be divided into three stages, namely, biological evolution (BE), cultural evolution (CE) and technological evolution (TE). BE is unable to redesign either its hardware or its software during its lifetime: both are determined by its DNA, and change only through evolution over many generations. In contrast, CE can redesign much of its software: humans can learn complex new skills—for example, languages, sports and professions—and can fundamentally update their worldview and goals. TE, which doesn't yet exist on Earth, can dramatically redesign not only its software but its hardware as well, rather than having to wait for it to gradually evolve over generations.

When and What?

After 13.8 billion years of cosmic evolution, development has accelerated dramatically here on Earth: BE arrived about 4 billion years ago, CE (we humans) arrived about a hundred millennia ago, and many AI researchers think that TE may arrive during the coming century, perhaps even during our lifetime, spawned by progress in AI. What will happen, and what will this mean for us? How are we to cope with Mohini's arrival?

The Arrival of Superhuman AI

There are various views among scholars, they are technosceptics who think that Superhuman AI will appear after 300 years and we need not worry now. Digital Utopians

also think the same and they also think that the arrival of Superhuman will definitely be a good thing. The beneficial AI movement feels that the concern is warranted and useful because AI safety research will have good outcome for humanity. Therefore, our efforts ought to be in the direction of co-existence and being relational with the Super-intelligent AI. Human beings are Being-in-the-world. They are not islands but connected even to the AI. So, making sense of their existence considering the ever-growing presence of AI is immensely important for the human existence.

Being Human - Relational - Collaborational

Human beings need to learn to be humans; so ‘being human’ is a dynamic process. Being human is about transcendence. Responding to the most basic instincts is animalistic and not human. Being human is a complex thing and requires conscious effort and civilization. Being human therefore is being rational, being social, and being emotional. Being human is not just for oneself but it is for the other. Therefore, being human in the age of AI is being relational, and being collaborational with AI without losing one’s humanness.

Can the Superhuman AI really match Human Intelligence (HI)?

Having postulated the arrival of Superhuman AI in the next century it would be to probe into their intelligence and can they match or supersede our intelligence? Would they be conscious and moral? These are all not scientific but philosophical questions. In short, the answer to these questions is no one knows for sure. Some might say it doesn’t matter: what the Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) will actually do is what’s important. However, our answers could affect how we *relate to them*, as we’ll see. *Being human* is ‘being social, relational, rational, vulnerable and being sexual’.

Friendly AI

Aligning the AI goals with the Human goals is a must otherwise things will go haywire and the humans will cede control to AI. Stephen Hawking has already envisaged this and he suggested that AI goals be aligned with that of humans: “Computers will overtake humans with AI within the next 100 years. When that happens, we need to make sure the computers have goals aligned with ours.”.

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If a superintelligence is ever unleashed, however, it will be the other way around: since intelligence is the ability to accomplish goals, a super-intelligent AI is by definition much better at accomplishing its goals than we humans are at accomplishing ours, and will therefore prevail. The real risk with AGI isn't *malice but their competence*. A super-intelligent AI will be extremely good at accomplishing its goals, and if those goals aren't aligned with ours, we're in trouble.

It splits into three tough subproblems, each of which is the subject of active research by computer scientists and other thinkers:

1. Making AI learn our goals
2. Making AI adopt our goals
3. Making AI retain our goals.

But even if you build an AI that will both learn and adopt our goals, you still haven't finished solving the goal-alignment problem: what if your AI's goals evolve as it gets smarter? How are we going to guarantee that it

retains our goals no matter how much recursive self-improvement it undergoes?

When we mention goals, whose goals are talking about? Of an individual or institute or a nation, or persons like Pope Francis, or Buddha, or Adishankara, or Adolf Hitler, or Modi?

Bhasmāsura's Destruction?

Although the enhancements in AI are making life easier for human beings day by day, there is constant fear that AI-based systems will pose a threat to humanity. People in the AI community have a diverse set of opinions regarding the pros and cons of AI mimicking human behavior. For example, a neural network trained to detect digits from the MNIST data set failed miserably when fed with test samples that are negative of the images, something that a human would have no issues with. Algorithms are reliable only to the extent of completeness of data used to train them. As always, garbage in implies garbage out.

Marriage of Mohini and Bhasmāsura

Instead of worrying about AI advancements, what if we can come out with a human-machine integrated strategy, including both human and machines, living together in a complex adaptive ecosystem? The human-machine integrated strategy for the future is not that of AI-enabled machines replacing humans but of machines and humans existing in a state of **sybiosis**. The most productive way to utilize AI is to use it to augment human capabilities. Machines do better at specific tasks while humans do better at general tasks. Therefore, a social setting where humans and machines interact while pushing or delegating tasks to each other, if they are not good at it, is an appropriate way to move forward.

There are several real-life tasks that cannot be accomplished completely by machines. Using human cognition

constructively in such tasks can help make problems easier for machines to solve. Researchers have for a long while attempted to make the interaction between humans and machines appear seamless and natural.

Machine Agents as Human Assistants

Humans are assisted by real-time machine agents to collaborate with diverse multi-cultural agents (sometimes speaking different languages). Machine agents provide necessary information and recommendations to humans, but the final decision is of the humans.

Fully Autonomous Machine Agents

An autonomous machine agent collaborates with other humans and machine agents. In this scenario, no human is responsible for the machine agent's actions. Hence this scenario is limited to those applications where the risk of the machine agent's actions is very low.

A Machine Agent Interacting with Humans

In this scenario, a machine agent is trained to understand and behave according to the preferences and goals of its human counterpart. A machine agent has the ability to negotiate and make decisions for its human. It works as an autonomous machine agent, but it refers back to its human counterpart when in doubt. So, the responsibility of actions taken by a machine agent lies with its human counterpart.

All Machine Agents Interaction

This is similar to the previous scenario in terms of how agents are trained and who bears the responsibility of actions taken by machine agents. The difference is that no humans are participating in the interaction. It poses different challenges in terms of how interactions take place among agents.

A Human Interacting with Machine Agents

This scenario points to a typical setting where a human walks into a special room in their house or office, where she can be immersed in the virtual environment of another group of people (remotely located) that she wants to collaborate with. All or part of the remote group may be represented by their machine agents (Mohanty, 2018).

Governance Framework

The following laws can be used along with the three laws of robotics:

1. Machine agents will never collect physical features such as skin colour, height, weight, etc. as visual input for the purposes of learning or identifying the cultural background of the individuals they cater to. The input will always need to be provided via a formal input channel. This is to make the system impervious to any stereotype associated with physical features.
2. A culturally insensitive remark, sentence, vocabulary, or slang will remain tagged insensitive to all cultures, unless its alternative positive aspect is clearly stated for a specific culture.
3. Human agents will need an active learning system, capable of incorporating feedback after an interaction, to continuously validate its behaviour

A clear “segregation of responsibility” and event-response matrix needs to be identified for both humans and machine agents. Humans and machine agents can then use enforced or automated activities to manage interdependencies and interaction.

Human Machine Relationship

The human-machine relationship is a symbiotic one where both entities are dependent on each other. While machines are

superior to humans in performing well-defined tasks, humans are superior in dynamic tasks that are not fully controlled and are affected by uncertain factors. Since real-life situations can consist of both types of tasks, the degree of freedom needs to be divided among humans and machines.

The Rhythm of the Algorithms

Contextualization: Algorithms present a very objective view leading to the final prediction. For example, they can make an accurate prediction on how a customer will react to an offer, but they can't pinpoint why the customer behaved the way he/she behaved! Therefore, contextualization is important.

Judgment skills: Algorithms are good at analyzing millions of data points and delivering precise recommendations; however, they lack the judgment skills that humans have.

Morality and the Mohini

The ability to be introspective has made us what we are. However, it seems that we are in a hurry to **outsource** this to algorithms. There are grave consequences for such an approach. We are pleased to see how automation is improving the quality of our lives, but we have not sat down and created a list of activities that we would never delegate (Mohanty & Vyas, 2018).

Robot's morality based on following three laws:

1. A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm.
2. A robot must obey any orders given to it by human beings, except where such orders would conflict with the First Law.

3. A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Law (Barrat, 2013).

Unemployment: The ethical question before us is, when more and more jobs are automated, what will we do with all the time on our hands? Our current employment contracts are based on one fundamental factor—we sell our time to earn enough to sustain ourselves and our families. So, if the prospect of time-based compensation goes away, we need to find newer ways to earn money.

How Will Machines Affect Human Behaviour?

1. Websites are designed by taking into the account the minutest levels of detail that would appeal to an individual's liking.
2. Recommendation engines push additional products to us by suggesting "people like you have bought these other things".
3. While you are driving past a supermall, your phone vibrates with a discount just for you.
4. Intelligent apps on our smartphone suggest which route to take to get to your destination faster.

How do we ensure that machines do not become biased?

Humans are not always fair and neutral. Machines also can exhibit similar unfair and irrational behaviour. AI systems are created by humans, thus there is a high likelihood that humans will introduce judgmental bias into the very machines they build. The ethical challenge before us is, if our future is going to be completely dependent on AI systems, we need to ensure that the machines perform as expected and aren't biased.

How do we keep AI safe from evil intentions?

What if AI agents become so focused on achieving their goals, that they recommend and implement things that may bring

disastrous consequences for us? For example, what if the goal of an AI system is to find solutions for cancer, and after careful considerations of numerous diagnosis results, root causes, treatment plans, and effectiveness of medicines, it realizes that the most effective and best way of solving the cancer problem is to kill everybody on the planet? From a machine's point of view, it has found the solution. From human point of view, it is catastrophic.

Singularity: Intelligence Explosion

Human evolution is almost entirely due to our intelligence and our ability to adapt to changing conditions. However, in our zest to invent more and more artificially super intelligent systems, we may get into a scenario where the machines are the most intelligent beings on earth, far superior than humans! This state is called “singularity”. Lynn said it with an all iterative flourish: “Bits and bytes can be as threatening as bullets and bombs.

Machine (AI) Rights

The ethical question before us is, once machines as entities attain sufficient maturity levels to see, sense, think, and act autonomously, they will demand a legal framework to protect and manage their share of rights. Should the intelligent machines be treated like humans?

Conclusion: Meta-Super-Intelligence

The revolutionary feats of AI are awe-inspiring. The humans have nothing to worry about the AI but to learn to **co-exist** with the AI. It is true that some imminent dangers are there, but that is the need of the hour. The humans are smart, they will evolve a system to counter any danger that haunts humanity. The human brain has already foreseen the dangers of Super-intelligent AI and working at co-existing with it.

I personally believe that the Super-intelligence would never allow it to destroy the universe where it lives. I'm optimistic about the AI turning into super-intelligent being, but that's not enough what we need is Meta-Super-intelligent-AI which will transcend the Super-intelligent-AI. When we say the Meta-super-intelligent being it is really 'meta', above the superintelligence.

The Bhasmāsura would know the seductive nature of the Mohini. The Meta-Superintelligence would let the AI look at Mohini not just with the lustful eyes but going even beyond that and seeing the Lord-Viṣṇu being veiled. This Meta-Super-intelligent, or the Meta-Mohini is here to wed the Bhasmāsura with the Humanity to transform the world for good. Of course, the Bhasmāsura has to divest himself of the Asura-ness. A true pursuit would be one that of Joy, Peace and Freedom. A true Meta-super-intelligent AI would surely bring about Joy, Peace and Freedom because the humans can be selfish but a Meta-super-intelligent AI would always be an altruistic artificial-being. Being human is to belong, even to the AI.

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Received April 14, 2020: Accepted May 12, 2020: Words: 3030

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